

Conference Abstract

The remarkable remipedes

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Abstract

This presentation will be a very general look at the exciting history of the crustacean class Remipedia, from discovering them in a water-filled cave in the Bahamas in 1979 to today. I will begin with an introduction to the beautiful remipede cave habitat. We will explore where these fascinating animals live and what other cave crustaceans inhabit their community.

I will review remipede research since publishing their description in the first volume of the Journal of Crustacean Biology in 1981 through 37 years of research. Several interesting remipede species will be highlighted for their unusual morphology. In closing I will propose questions to encourage future research with these interesting crustaceans.

Presenting author

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